

Fake Currency Detection using image processing

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Abstract - A significant challenge for ordinary individuals is distinguishing genuine banknotes, especially with the rise in counterfeit currency production, which harms the economy by reducing the value of real money and causing inflation. To address this issue, a proposed solution utilizes OpenCV to determine whether a given banknote is genuine or counterfeit, employing advanced image processing and computer vision techniques. This system is particularly relevant in India where paper currency is widely used, emphasizing the importance of ensuring the authenticity of banknotes in daily transactions.

Keywords – Fake currency, image processing, Gray-Scale Conversion, Feature extraction, ORB Detector

I. INTRODUCTION

Detecting counterfeit Indian currency notes has become increasingly challenging due to the lack of advanced technologies specifically designed for this purpose. While numerous studies have been conducted to address this issue, the technology landscape continues to evolve, necessitating regular updates to detection systems. Indian currency notes, both old and new, possess unique features, making it difficult to distinguish between genuine and fake bills. With the rise of technology, counterfeit currency production has surged, posing a significant challenge for researchers. There is a growing demand for user-friendly fake currency detection machines that can accurately identify counterfeit notes in circulation. These detection systems aim to tackle the problem of counterfeit currency by employing innovative techniques and technologies.

The system under consideration is tailored for the validation of Indian currency note with denominations of 500 rupees. Several algorithms are employed in the process, including image acquisition, pre-processing, greyscale conversion, feature extraction, image segmentation, and comparison using techniques like ORB and SSIM. Subsequently, the system verifies the authenticity of currency notes by examining the bleed lines and number panels.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

L. Latha Et al [1]

The paper aims to tackle the rising issue of counterfeit currency manufacturing in India through the introduction of a detection method leveraging image processing techniques.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11184447](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11184447)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

Authors employ OpenCV and machine learning to differentiate between authentic and counterfeit currency notes, emphasizing edge detection, greyscale conversion, image segmentation, and characteristic extraction. The proposed system targets the provision of a precise and accessible solution for identifying fake currency, with the ultimate goal of reducing the economic repercussions associated with counterfeit notes.

Sagar Shinde Et al [2]

The objective of this paper is to tackle the escalating problem of counterfeit currency notes in India by creating a system proficient in swiftly identifying fake notes. Employing image processing methodologies and tools like MATLAB, the system endeavors to authenticate Indian currency notes by extracting diverse attributes like Bleed Line, Watermarking, Fluorescence, Security Thread, Micro Lettering, and Identification Mark. Capitalizing on Support Vector Machine and alternative techniques, the proposed system prioritizes velocity, simplicity, and precision in discerning between authentic and counterfeit currency notes.

Nagendra Kumar Et al [3]

The objective of this study is to tackle the issue of identifying counterfeit currency in financial transactions, specifically in countries like India, the United States, and Europe, where counterfeiting presents a major challenge. The study suggests leveraging modern technological advancements, such as spectral imaging and analysis, to automate the process of identifying counterfeit currency with speed and precision. By examining images taken in different spectral bands and extracting additional features from both genuine and counterfeit currency notes, the study aims to devise a holistic approach for differentiating between authentic and counterfeit currency.

Aman Bhatia Et al [4]

This paper aims to investigate and suggest an approach for identifying counterfeit currency through the utilization of machine learning algorithms and image processing methods. Particularly, the study intends to exploit the effectiveness of the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm, known for its high accuracy with small datasets, to discern fake currency. By establishing a banknote authentication dataset and employing computational and mathematical techniques, the research endeavors to precisely extract and scrutinize

features pertinent to currency authenticity, thereby attaining accurate detection of counterfeit notes.

Asha Banu Et al [5]

This paper proposes a method for detecting fake Indian currency notes using image processing techniques implemented in MATLAB. The approach involves image acquisition, gray scale conversion, edge detection using Canny's algorithm, image segmentation, and extraction of features. The features extracted include the serial number, authenticity mark, and portrait of Mahatma Gandhi. The intensity of these features is calculated, and if it exceeds a threshold of 70%, the note is considered authentic; otherwise, it's deemed fake.

III. MOTIVATION

Identifying whether Indian currency is fake or real is a big problem at present. Use of fake currency is reduce the value of real currency. Therefore ,a system to detect fake currency is essential. There are so many features in Indian currency should be difficult to compare. The main objective of this system is identify the fake currency using computer vision techniques and image processing.

- The system should have user-friendly interfaces that allow users to upload currency images, generate outputs, and determine whether the currency is real or fake.
- The system should be generate a output in short time period

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to detect currency authenticity using the ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF) feature detection and matching algorithm, along with SSIM (Structural Similarity Index Measure).Detected Features are compared with test images and structural similarity index(SSIM)is calculated to assess similarity. The process involves the counting and verification of bleed lines and the detection of characters in the number panel of currency notes, comprising several steps.

- Data Collection
- Data Preprocessing
- Grayscale Conversion
- Feature Detection using ORB
- Feature comparison using SSIM

A. Data Collection: Data collection is a process of collecting the data in different source. Prepare the dataset in 500 currency notes. The various 10 features are present in the currency dataset that are:

Fig.1-500 rupee,dataset image

- Ashoka pillar Emblem(1 feature)
- RBI Symbols (2 features)
- RBI logo(1 feature)
- Representation of "Rs. 500" in both Devanagari and English scripts (2 features)
- Bleed Lines (2 features)
- Number Panel (1 feature)

B. Data Pre-processing : Data Pre-processing is resize the images into fixed size. Preparing data for analysis by removing or modifying data that is incorrect, incomplete, irrelevant, duplicated, or improperly formatted

C. Grey-scale conversion: The obtained image is converted to black and white, eliminating hue and saturation information while retaining luminance.

D. ORB (Oriented Fast and rotated BRIEF): Feature detection is performed using ORB.The datasets which contains ten different security features. Multiple images with varying brightness of each security feature are included in the dataset. The ORB algorithm is used to detect each security feature in the test image. Then extract the feature of each test images.

E. Feature comparison using SSIM: In this approach, the original template is compared with the extracted feature, and a score is assigned to measure the similarity between the two images using SSIM. Basically it is look for the similarity between each images. SSIM takes into account luminance, contrast, and structure similarities between the images, providing a value between -1 and 1, where 1 indicates perfect similarity. Higher SSIM values indicate greater similarity between the images.

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)}$$

This algorithm calculates the average and maximum SSIM scores for each feature. A feature is considered genuine if its average SSIM score exceeds a predetermined minimum value, determined through rigorous testing.

Next counts the number of bleed lines present on the left and right edges of currency notes, which are essential

security features It identifies black regions in each column and calculates the average count of non-erroneous columns, providing the total number of bleed lines. For Rs 500 currency notes, the expected count is approximately 5.

V. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the Recognition of Indian currency. While building the model user uses the algorithms. Images are readed using OpenCV, Features are found using ORB and matches are found using SSIM. The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import cv2
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from skimage.metrics import structural_similarity as ssim |
from tkinter import *
from tkinter.ttk import Progressbar
```

2. Read and resize the test image.

```
test_img = cv2.imread(path)
test_img = cv2.resize(test_img, (1167, 519))
```

3. Test image is converted into Grayscale

```
gray_test_image = cv2.cvtColor(test_img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
```

4. Find the feature detection and extraction using ORB.

```
orb = cv2.ORB_create(
    nfeatures,
    scaleFactor,
    edgeThreshold)
kpts1, desc1 = orb.detectAndCompute(template_img, None)
kpts2, desc2 = orb.detectAndCompute(query_img, None)
```

5. Calculating SSIM of the two images sent as a parameters

```
def calculateSSIM(template_img, query_img):
    min_w = min(template_img.shape[1], query_img.shape[1])
    min_h = min(template_img.shape[0], query_img.shape[0])
```

6. Iteration over each row and column in the image of bleed lines

```
for j in range(width):
    col = thresh[:, j:j+1]
    count = 0
    for i in range(len(col)-1):
        pixel1_value = col[i][0]
        pixel2_value = col[i+1][0]
```

VI. RESULT

This result shows the most appropriate matching in the resultant image. SSIM helps to find the best matches in the images. If 10 out of 10 feature passed it should be real currency and less than 10 feature passed it should be fake

currency. It should showing the average SSIM score and Maximum SSIM score

RESULT: 6 / 10 features PASSED!
Fig 2-Output (Fake note)

RESULT: 10 / 10 features PASSED!
Fig 3- Output (Real note)

Fig 4 – Output Calculation using SSIM

Fig 5 – Output Of Features

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The proposed system presents a robust solution for detecting counterfeit Indian currency notes by leveraging advanced image processing and computer vision techniques. Through the utilization of algorithms such as ORB for feature detection and SSIM for feature comparison, the system effectively distinguishes between genuine and fake currency notes.

The implementation of this system has the potential to significantly decrease the circulation of counterfeit

currency nationwide, thereby offering substantial benefits in various sectors such as markets, banks, and other venues where currency exchanges occur frequently. Looking ahead, there is a prospect to develop a mobile application specifically designed for the Android platform, catering to individuals with disabilities, particularly those with visual impairments. Such an application could provide valuable assistance to visually challenged individuals in verifying currency authenticity, thus promoting greater inclusivity and accessibility in financial transactions.

VIII. REFERENCE

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DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.11184447**

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